

RL-based control for wearable robotics: a summary

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Abstract

Wearable robotics (WR) has emerged as an instrument of great utility and potential in assistance and rehabilitation therapies for patients with different motor conditions. Modern artificial intelligence, and specifically Reinforcement Learning (RL) techniques, makes possible the design of advanced algorithms capable of carrying out real-time adaptations to the user's needs, generally through movement intention recognition. This paper summarizes the current state of the art on RL-based control methods for wearable robots, e.g., gait rehabilitation exoskeletons. To this end, a literature review was carried out, selecting the most novel and promising methodologies, as well as the problems encountered, sensorization, realistic models or digital twins, the development of adaptive control models, the difficulties of the models' deployment outside the simulation, and the challenges that the community and research groups face in the coming years.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wearable robots (WRs), e.g., exoskeletons, appeared as a very helpful asset for the human therapist in rehabilitation and assistive applications. But these robotic devices are not only thought for the healthcare domain but for the industry preventing physical deterioration and augmenting capacities and even for final consumers to do sports or assist at home in the presence of mobility disabilities (e.g., elderly population). In essence, WRs are body extensions that can assist, substitute and augment physical capabilities to maintain quality of life in terms of mobility. However, this endeavor still presents several challenges due to the complex triadic physical interaction between the robot, the human body and the environment, which differs from other autonomous robotic solutions. Thus, actuation and control should adhere to very particular requirements of safety and compliance with the human body [1]. Furthermore, the WR must adapt to different users and different applications and contexts. These particularities have prevented achieving the full potential of WRs in usability and generalization.

The use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning in WRs has raised an opportunity for improving their usability in several aspects. For instance, the design of new tools to improve the supervision and quality of therapies, as therapeutic adjuncts to facilitate clinical practice. Its effectiveness has been shown for patients suffering from neurological impairments such as stroke and spinal cord injuries increasing the independence and mobility of patients [2], [3]. AI state of the art in WRs can be found in several reviews, such as [2], [4]–[6]. Medical and rehabilitation publications focus separately on the lower and upper limbs. WRs for upper limbs are more feasible due to a constant reference point (shoulder axis). For instance, [5] surveyed the application of machine learning techniques in robot-assisted upper limb rehabilitation. They analysed movement intention recognition methods (physical and physiological signals) and human-robot interactive control (based on neural networks (NN) and (RL)). However, the majority of the research works focused on the lower limbs given their relevance on human gait. [6] explored the role of machine learning in gait analysis, identifying Support Vector Machine (SVM) as a prominent classifier based on an analysis of 43 distinct studies. [2] studies the application of machine learning techniques for rehabilitation robots for lower limbs grouped into four categories according to the AI methodology adopted, RL, NNs, SVMs, and Decision Trees.

Despite this large recent literature, in terms of smooth shared control between the user and the robot, there is a large room for improvement. Nowadays, PID control techniques with open-loop trajectory generation prevail. For instance, the walking trajectory profile is given by the designer, and the movement of the leg is triggered by timing or through muscle activation patterns detection using EMG sensors [7]. More advanced model predictive control techniques are also under research mainly in prosthetic applications [8].

Surprisingly, data-driven learning applied to control methods, such as Deep Reinforcement Learning (DeepRL), which is revolutionizing sophisticated and hard-to-engineer robotics behaviours allowing adaptation in different situations (e.g., drones flight [9] and quadruped walking [10]), is still in a very early stage in the WR field [4].

RL techniques applied in the field of robotics appeared in 1992 with [11] but it is in 2010 when the first studies in WRs started to be published, experiencing an exponential growth and doubling the number of publications in 2020, this growth is expected to continue in the coming years (Figure 1). Despite its potential, the reasons for this slowdown in RL technology adoption in the WR field may be the strong safety requirements of an actuated robot attached to a human body, the complexity of the interaction, which needs to be modelled or captured in the training data, and the diversity of body shapes (personalization) and applications (generalization).

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Fig. 1: Publications per year on WR control-based RL with a moving average since 2010. Obtained from Scopus

A generally agreed definition of RL is: a computational approach for learning from the environment interaction focused on goal-directed learning by maximizing an expected future reward function [11]. Applied to the WR field, the exoskeleton observes the environment (e.g., human-exo interactions, experiment area) and chooses the best action, which generates the desired trajectory, over a pull of potential actions based on the current state of the system and environment observation. This value selection process is governed by a priority guide called policy (originally state-action pair). Solving the RL problem is to find a policy that optimizes the long-term sum of rewards (optimal policy) via policy improvement techniques (Figure 2).

Fig. 2: RL selection process scheme in WRs

From the range of applications of RL to robotic devices, such as parameter tuning [12], [13], compliance adaptation [14], [15], and control, we are interested in learning methods to control the WR. The robot learns through data to generate and adapt its behaviour according to the task and the user's intention. Hence, this survey focuses on: 1) showcasing current RL or DeepRL methods for WRs applied for rehabilitation, 2) describing the current landscape of approaches, and 3) identifying challenges to unlock the full potential of RL in the WR field.

II. SURVEY METHODOLOGY

A comprehensive literature search is performed, updated until May 2024, across Scopus, Web of Science and Google Scholar databases. The following keywords were used to guide our search: *(Reinforcement Learning OR Deep Reinforcement Learning) AND (Exoskeleton OR Wearable Robot OR Rehabilitation)*. Inclusion criteria and PRISMA flowchart of our search (Figure 3) are summarized as follows:

- The publication date of the study should be after 2020, published in reputable journals or international conferences to ensure the validity and reliability of the works considered for inclusion in the analysis.

TABLE I: Selected papers.

Feature	Representative work	Model	Subjects
RL control for squat assistance	[16]	PPO	Sim
Deep-RL for gait control	[17]	PPO	Sim
RL control for stabilize walking	[18]	PPO	Sim
RL assistive control for walk, run and climb stairs	[26]	PPO	Sim
Deep-RL control for gait trajectory plannig	[19]	DPPO	Sim
Deep-RL for gait control	[20]	DDPG	Sim
Deep-RL for EMG control exoskeleton	[21]	TD3	Sim
Deep-RL for gait control	[22]	TD3	Sim
RL control for mirror therapy	[23]	NAF	5 Hemiplegic patient
Deep-RL control for ankle exoskeleton	[24]	SAC	Sim
RL control for knee exoskeleton in spasticity conditions	[27]	SAC	Sim
Deep-RL for walking assistance control	[25]	ACNN	3 Healthy

- The study should focus on the application of RL or DeepRL for control in assistance or rehabilitation applications.
- The study should be a practical implementation (simulation or real) of a lower or upper limb exoskeleton, discarding pure theoretical approaches of new learning methods.
- The working conditions, hyperparameters and features should be clearly stated for replicating the training process and implementing the proposed approach to consider the study eligible.

Fig. 3: PRISMA flowchart diagram of the search and identification process.

III. DEEP RL METHODS FOR WRS

To maximize the sum of expected reward of continuous variables within RL, a policy improvement technique is needed. Table I presents the most common policies used in the selected papers. This includes Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) [16]–[18], Distributed Proximal Policy Optimization (DPPO) [19], Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG) [20], Twin Delayed Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (TD3) [21], [22], Normalized Advantage Function (NAF) [23], Soft-Actor-Critic (SAC) [24] and a modify Actor-Critic Neural Network (ACNN) [25].

A. Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO)

Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) is a model-free policy gradient algorithm that samples data through interaction with the environment and optimizes a “surrogate” objective function. It utilizes a trust region constraint to force the control policy update and ensure that the new policy is not too far away from the old policy [28]. [16] proposes a motion controller reinforcement learning-based for a lower extremity rehabilitation exoskeleton focused on collaborative squatting exercises. The used rehabilitation exoskeleton has ankle actuation on sagittal and front planes and is equipped with multiple foot force sensors. This proposed motion controller estimates Center of Pressure (CoP), an important indicator of system balance, and incorporates it in the state input of the control policy network and the reward function. Dynamics randomization and adversary force perturbations are used during the training to further improve control robustness. This training is realized using a model free control policy network PPO and connected Multi-Layer Perception (MLP) neural network with the agent of RL algorithm. RL algorithm selects according to its policy the desired joint position at each moment and a Proportional Derivative (PD) motor controller obtains smooth motions and actions. To evaluate the effectiveness of the learning controller, results are shown for 3 cases; Case 1, without external perturbation achieving an average joint angle tracking error of 1.22 degrees compared with the target squatting motion, Case 2, simulation of perturbation forces resulting in an average joint angle tracking error of 2.64 degrees and Case 3, human-exoskeleton interactions without muscle contraction, considering the user as a Spinal Cord Injury (SCI) or stroke patient with very limited or no muscle control, obtaining an average joint angle tracking error of 2.49 degrees.

[17] presents a robust controller for a lower limb rehabilitation exoskeleton, this time for walking assisting in users with different disabilities as quadriplegic, muscle weakness or hemiplegic conditions without any control parameter tuning based on a decoupled offline human-exoskeleton simulation training with three independent networks. These networks are muscle coordination network, motion imitation network and interaction network. The last two have been trained by PPO learning method. The proposed method enables the trained control policy to use only proprioceptive information (joints encoder data) of the exoskeleton regardless of the uncertain human-exoskeleton interaction forces, although there is no physical implementation, they state that this approach allows for easier deployment. Results have been obtained in 200 simulated environments with different dynamics, measuring an RMSE of joint tracking accuracy below 5 degrees and predicted joint torques less than 100 Nm operating at about 9.3 A DC current.

[18] is developing a so-called cyber-physical walking system (CPWS) for SCI paralyzed patients consists of a functional neuromuscular stimulation system and a powered lower-limb exoskeleton. The model has a total of 12 degrees of freedom (DOF), 6 DOF on each leg, and torso is assumed fixed by the exoskeleton corset brace. [18] designs two different methods called local and global method for exoskeleton control. Local method is composed by different neural networks separated for each action control task, foot placement controller and stance leg controller, the aim of this method is to facilitate the optimization task as compared to the optimization of a single more complex control system. Global method consists of a unique neural network responsible for controlling both systems. The training algorithm used in this work is PPO because they maintain that it is efficient compared to other on-policy stochastic policy gradient methods and it is straightforward to implement. Torque forces of torso and way-points are used as input of reward function. The simulated results (local method) obtained for biped walks at a steady pace in a range of 0.7 to 1.3 m/s are a way-point following precision of 0.3m with a disturbance below to 400 N in torso. These tests were done for human models of different statures from 1.4 to 2.2 m tall without any control parameters changes.

The focus of [19] is to show the improvement of using DPPO method over conventional DeepRL in continuous space such as Asynchronous Advantage Actors (AC3) to increase the convergence and learning rate during RL training. To demonstrate this approach proposes two dense reward functions based on DeepRL methods for an upper-limb rehabilitation exoskeleton trajectory planning. In this approach the DDPG method is restricted for a long experience replay and proposes and Distributed PPO (DPPO) introducing a penalty term to reduce the impact of unreasonable learning rate by providing a more reasonable update proportion. Each reward function has different objectives, the most interesting, the azimuth reward, provides a global guidance and reasonable constraints in the exploration and aspiration reward capable of accelerating the exploration process and avoid locally optimal solution. Results show that the use of both reward functions are able to accelerate the convergence rate by 38.4% using DPPO over AC3 method. Also the mean of convergence increases by 9.5% and the percentage of standard deviation decreases by 21.2% to 23.3%.

[26] presents a "Experiment-free exoskeleton assistance learning in simulation", using an architecture with three different RL networks to achieve a successfully real exoskeleton deployment without physical training. The first RL network is a motion imitation network with a reward function optimized to maintain balance during walking taking as input the human state measured with an Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) connected to the thigh and a human gait dataset. The second network is a muscles coordination network providing as the output a muscles activation array based on joint torques input generated during gait or MS state. The last network is the exoskeleton control network, that provides exoskeleton torques taking into account the muscle human effort reduction as a principal component of its reward function. The learned controller is deployed on a custom hip exoskeleton made in previous works that automatically generates assistance across different tasks with reduced metabolic rates by 24.3%, 13.1% and 15.4% for walking, running and stair climbing, respectively.

B. Deep Deterministic Policy Gradient (DDPG)

DDPG is an off-policy, model-free, actor-critic DeepRL technique adding on Deep Deterministic Gradient technique a neural network Q function approximators which uses batch learning for stability [29]. However, this approach has a notably limitation: as with most model-free reinforcement approaches, DDPG requires a large number of training episodes to find solutions.

[20] presents a new model-free DeepRL method for end-to-end learning of desired gait patterns for over-ground gait rehabilitation with an exoskeleton without requiring a predefined dynamics model. Their approach is the first one using DDPG algorithm to exoskeleton control composed of an actor and critic neural networks. The Exoskeleton used is H2 from Technaid with hip, knee and ankle actuators paired with musculoskeletal model generated in Opensim. In each time step of training the observations are composed by torque and velocity of the exoskeleton actuators, joint angles, velocities and accelerations of the musculoskeletal (MK) model and the current error for each joint based on the desired joint angles for all three joints of the MK model. Their simulated results during a gait cycle have a Mean absolute error for all joint falls below 0.5 degrees, with a Standar deviation below 0.2 degrees.

C. Twin-Delayed DDPG (TD3)

TD3 is an DDPG improvement developed to reduce the growth of convergence errors due to the reward overestimation, improving the stability conditions, and regularizing the action noise [30].

[21] proposes a DeepRL method to control the assistance level of an upper-limb exoskeleton in real-time based on the electromyographic (EMG) activity of human muscles. The proposed autonomous assistive device would enhance the force exertion capability of individuals identifying scaling factors for personalized amplification of their effort without lengthy offline training. A TD3 method for rapid learning of the appropriate controller's gain values and delivering personalized assistive torques is employing based on a nonlinear reward function defined by the observation of the motion response, the human EMG activity and the angle deviation from the destination point to minimize the muscle effort and maximize the positioning accuracy simultaneously. The proposed DeepRL method is able to identify the appropriate assistive gain for each joint of the exoskeleton in real-time. On simulated experiments with a 4 kg weight handling task, they obtained optimal handling with less than 15% of the muscle contraction level (EMG activity).

[22] proposes an end-to-end controller for a lower-limb exoskeleton for human performance augmentation. It is the only paper using exoskeletons as rehabilitation robots based on DeepRL. Contains two control levels: a high-level control based on DeepRL and a low control level for motion tracking by joint PD controllers. The high control level uses a TD3 agent as learning algorithm which contains one actor network and two twin delayed critic networks that share the same architecture but have separate learnable weight and bias parameters. This controller is responsible for human motion intention recognition tacking into account the exoskeleton state signals, the human-exoskeleton interaction, the joints force signals (generated by deep neural network predictor). The deep neural network predictor deletes complex kinematic calculations required in conventional human motion intention recognition methods. A passive mode (all joints remain unpowered) is introduced as a a performance assessment for comparison purposes and proposed method based on Human-Exo Interactions (HEI) forces. On the simulated results the global ratio of the HEI forces for a gait experiment using the DeepRL controller mode compared to passive mode is low as 0.65.

D. Normalized Advantage Function (NAF)

The main idea of NAF consists in the approximation of the Q-function with quadratic functions. NAF representation allows to apply Q-learning with experience replay to continuous tasks, and substantially improves performance on a set of simulated robotic control tasks [31].

In [23] a robotic framework is proposed for hemiparesis rehabilitation based on mirror therapy applied to transfer the patient's healthy limb movements to the impaired limb. The healthy limb joints motions are mimicked by the impaired limb with the assistance of a wearable robot, stimulating and strengthening the injured muscles. The system proposed in this research is a master-slave robotic system and the reinforcement learning algorithm is responsible of the human-robot interaction control improving rehabilitation efficacy and safety. The inputs and sensed information of the environment are joints motion trajectory, muscle activation via EMG and user's emotion via facial expression recognition. The reinforcement learning approach for assisted robot is realized by a model free and continuous domain NAF algorithm. The proposed method has a physical implementation on five, post-stroke, hemiplegic patients obtaining results in position tracking below to 2,86 degrees of mean error and 0.33 rad/s of angular joint velocity mean error.

E. Soft-Actor-Critic (SAC)

Is a policy improvement method for data-expensive environments where the agent has to interact with a real-world. In contrast to other optimization methods, SAC modifies the policy objective by augmenting rewards with additional policy entropy [32].

[24] presents a robotic orthosis controller considering physical human-robot interaction via dynamic simulation based on two-stage policy training framework DeepRL. First a policy responsible to generating human healthy gaits based imitation learning, and second, for human models in which the right soleus muscle is weakened due to a certain severity modified from first model. A robotic orthosis is paired to the right ankle of these models. The orthosis policy that assists walking with optimal torque is then trained on these models. For human policy reward the joint angle, angular velocity and muscular activation via EMG are tacking account and for orthosis policy reward are joint angle, angular velocity and joint torque. [24] has a physical implementation measuring muscle activation during gait, with integrated EMG of the gastrocnemius, and obtaining a reduction of 9.12% compared to the case without assistance.

In [33] describes a novel adaptive torque controller via deep reinforcement learning for a knee exoskeleton under joint spasticity conditions, which accounts for task performance and interaction forces reduction obtained from joint angle, angular velocity and joint torque, as a principal components of the reward function. To train the RL agent, a digital twin is developed, including a musculoskeletal-exoskeleton system with joint misalignment and a differentiable spastic reflexes model for the muscles activation. Results for a simulated knee extension movement showed that the agent learns to control the exoskeleton for individuals with different levels of spasticity. The proposed controller was able to reduce maximum torques applied to the human joint under spastic conditions by an average of 10.6% and decreases the root mean square until the settling time by 8.9% compared to a conventional compliant controller.

F. Actor-Critic Neural Network (ACNN)

A Data-Driven Reinforcement Learning (DDRL) control proposed in [25] as a strategy to gait assistance for different hemiplegic patients with unpredictable disturbances. The interaction between exoskeleton lower limbs and the legs of a hemiplegic patient are modelled as a slave-master framework. The approach is transforming the walking assistance control problem into an optimal control problem learning by a policy iteration algorithm. To achieve a high level of adaptation control for different patients, an Actor Critic Neural Network (ACNN) technology for the DeepRL algorithm is employed. The inputs of the reward function are the angle and torque for hip and knee exoskeleton joints and the joint angle collected from human via IMU. The experiments were realized on a simulation environment and on AIDER real system.

IV. CHALLENGES

While the application of RL and DeepRL for wearable robotics is expected to revolutionise the field in the coming years, a number of scientific and technological challenges are still needed to be addressed:

a) Sensorization: Control methods based on DeepRL, especially model-free approaches, are data-driven learning methods through information obtained from the user (or musculoskeletal model in simulation) and the WR. This requires the WR to feature multiple sensors, which adds considerable weight and increases the complexity of the system, as well as sensors to the human (usually EMG) that greatly hinders the mobility, adaptation and quality of the therapies performed with real pathological patients [34]. Therefore, an important research topic is to derive the minimal number and type of sensors required to apply RL-based control algorithms in WRs. The developed exoskeleton should be able to train with different DeepRL algorithms obtaining an optimal policy only using the data obtained from the device (e.g. joint angle or position, angular velocity, joint torque and pressure sensors).

b) Advanced control: The reviewed papers focus on the development of control algorithms for specific problems, insufficient for the total of actions or activities that the user must be able to perform to develop an optimal quality of life. Thus, a current challenge is the design of an algorithm including more than one possible motion policy capable to adapt it to more complex tasks and user interactions. Some authors proposed to investigate the implementation of neural networks for high-level control, abstracting the AI problem to a higher level, allowing to choose among several optimal policies depending on the activity performed. However, one of the most important challenges is to provide adaptive force/torque control to the WR. The methods reviewed only address position control.

c) Digital twins: We identified that the challenges are not only focused on the development of RL algorithms. The design of realistic simulation environments and reliable human and WR digital twins presents notable problems on the human-exoskeleton interactions modeling. Currently, physical interactions and behaviours modeling are mathematical simplifications of the problem. This difficulty is encountered on the literature, finding that most of publications reviewed and presented in this study are focused on model-free (80%), improving their policy based on raw data without taking into account or developing a realistic simulation environment (digital twin).

d) Physical deployment and Safety: PPO is the most frequently reinforcement learning method used in the WR field. However, none of these studies (40% of total) presented a real implementation of the algorithm in a real WR, being limited to demonstrations in simulation. In fact, the implementation rate of RL in real WRs based on our review is only of 20%. Consequently it is estimated that an enormous difficulty is currently being encountered in the transition from simulated experiments to physical prototypes interacting with real users. Therefore, one of the major challenges the exoskeleton DeepRL community will face in the coming years will be to show the efficacy and performance of simulation-based trained algorithms into real WR prototypes that are able to interact with humans while prioritizing on safety and comfort under all working conditions.

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